

How Can Hearst Bridge the Intention-Behaviour Gap Towards Fast Fashion Using the Theory of Planned Behaviour?

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ABSTRACT

Well-known publications like Harper's Bazaar, Elle, Cosmopolitan, and more make up Hearst's powerful digital media portfolio, which is built on editorial skills, audience data, and intelligence. Hearst's mission is to enable its audience and partners to succeed and enjoy life to the fullest. Hearst UK had more than 79 million social media likes and followers as of 2022, delivered 4 million publications each month, and engaged with 26 million online users (Hearst, 2022).

Acknowledging the growing market value of fast fashion and its impact on the environment, Hearst has raised concerns about the issue of unsustainable consumption despite consumers' presumed attitude (intention-behaviour gap) towards sustainability. Insight from market and academic research has identified language as one of the root causes of this gap.

The theory of planned behaviour (TPB) was selected to further provide insights into factors influencing intentions, which then forecast behaviour. The TPB argues that perceptions of behavioural control, subjective norms, and attitude all affect human behavioural intention. The recommendation proposed was intentional, in order to help inform, educate, and transform the habits of Hearst consumers. Hearst should consider incorporating this suggestion into their marketing and advertising plan to have the greatest impact in changing the behaviour of its customers.

OBJECTIVE

Although media coverage of climate change and the environmental effects of fast fashion clearly has a significant impact on consumers, this influence doesn't always translate into changes in behaviour or attitudes. In fact, 72% of buyers state that it is simpler for them to purchase fashionable things from fast fashion brands than to search for eco-friendly alternatives. To this end, the objective of this report is to bridge the value-action gap in fast fashion, thereby increasing sustainable consumption among Hearst's audience by the fourth quarter of 2023

BACKGROUND TO STUDY

According to Amed et al. (2019), the market value of the global fashion business has been rising, which is related to the increasing "fast fashion" phenomenon on a worldwide scale. Given that only 1% of clothing is supposedly produced responsibly, the fashion industry is one of the highest waste generators on the planet. Fast fashion has been criticised for promoting excessive consumerism, which wastes resources, adds to pollution, and accelerates climate change. Unsold items from mass production frequently end up in landfills.

Customers and brands alike are becoming increasingly concerned about environmental and social issues related to the fashion industry. Despite assumptions that the cost-of-living crisis will have a negative impact on sustainability, consumers will likely go for cheaper alternatives, thereby trading quality for quantity. A study on fashion and sustainability reveals that 57% of all Britons still value sustainability when making fashion purchases. There has been a significant shift in how people shop for clothing items; this is all thanks to the pandemic and lifestyle changes. With the majority of responses asserting that inflation has raised their awareness of the significance of sustainable fashion, it is clear that the squeeze on incomes is causing major changes in how people shop for clothing.

Contrary to the taken-for-granted assumption that consumers are not interested in sustainability, hence the rise in fast fashion, insights reveal that consumers are actually aware of the dangers of fast fashion, the importance of sustainability, and sustainable consumption and are actually interested in sustainable living. Nonetheless, consumers' enthusiasm has slightly reduced in recent months compared to when the pandemic was at its peak. According to the most recent study, 57% of respondents now prioritise sustainability when buying clothing, dropping from 60% in 2021 (Mintel, 2022).

As initially mentioned, consumers are aware of and interested in sustainable fashion, yet their actions are counterproductive (Connell, 2011). This suggests that persuading consumers to act in a sustainable manner is a very tricky task. Therefore, it has become crucial for both marketers and decision-makers to figure out how to motivate customers to act sustainably.

Research in the field of sustainable fashion shows that there is an attitude-behaviour gap, otherwise known as the intention-behaviour gap, which may be caused by several factors that prevent consumers from adopting sustainable fashion. Brandão and Costa, (2021) citing existing research, highlighted the higher cost of sustainable options, the lack of style and aesthetics, the lack of availability and accessibility to sustainably produced goods, the lack of knowledge of fast fashion's environmental impact, and scepticism toward sustainable claims as some of the hindrances to sustainable consumption in the context of fashion (Connell, 2010; Diddi *et al.*, 2019; Harris *et al.*, 2016; McNeill and Moore, 2015; Moon *et al.*, 2014; Ozturk and Engizek, 2017). This report, however focuses on language as a major trigger for a lack of trust and scepticism.

KEY ISSUE

To influence desires and illicit behavioural change, it is imperative to communicate in a language that the audience understands. Marketers and brands alike have swapped out simple layman's phrases that consumers are familiar with, like "pollution," for more ambiguous words like "carbon footprint." Language is an effective tactic for influencing consumers' desires and behaviours. It is important to note that language has a huge impact on how people think. The primary element of communication is language. As highlighted by UNESCO, language is significant because it allows for communication, shared meaning, and a sense of individualism and communal identity. Since communication is essential to development, it is safe to say that language plays a crucial role in influencing sustainable consumption (Traoré, 2017).

Marketers frequently use the influential power of advertising appeals to persuade consumers to adopt sustainable habits (Goldstein, Cialdini, & Griskevicius, 2008). The abstract appeal is a typical type of appeal; this kind of appeal uses vague or subjective language and uses unspecific or generalised words to explain the qualities of sustainable products. This appeal is almost like an emotional strategy. While adopting an abstract appeal, terms like pollution, eco-friendly, clean, thrift, and second-hand are utilised. The rational strategy, on the other hand, is the concrete appeal. This, in contrast, provides in-depth details with concrete evidence and consistently illustrates the qualities of sustainable products in a more definite or objective manner (Leonidou et al., 2011).

For concrete appeals, terms like "carbon footprint," "net zero," "carbon neutral," "biodegradable," etc. are used. It is no news that there is a lot of content regarding sustainability and sustainable consumption, and in most cases, a concrete appeal strategy is used, which honestly causes information overload and a lack of interest. The issue is that while people who work in CSR and sustainability understand these terms, the majority of the general population does not. Research reveals that when "NetZero" is discussed, people either don't understand it or believe it to be greenwashing, which is not surprising.

Previous findings show that adopting various advertising appeals can drastically alter customers' views and behaviours toward sustainable consumption. (Yang et al., 2015). At this junction, the debate is whether Hearts should employ more emotional and abstract language in their content aimed at sustainable consumption. However, the setback with using just an abstract appeal is the issue of trust. 74% of customers have a hard time figuring out whether fashion brands' sustainability claims are sincere and credible. The practice of "greenwashing," in which a business makes exaggerated or misleading claims about its environmental credentials, is widely known to consumers (Mintel, 2022).

WHY HEARST?

Built on editorial expertise, audience data, and insight, well-known titles such as Harper's Bazaar, Elle, Cosmopolitan, etc., make up Hearst's very robust digital media portfolio. Hearst's goal is to create purposeful content that empowers its partners and audience to achieve success and get more out of life. As of 2022, Hearst UK distributed 4 million publications monthly, interacted with 26 million internet users, and had over 79 million social media likes and followers (Hearst, 2022).

Hearst's strong brand authority and market presence categorise the brand as an opinion leader in the fashion industry. As a digital platform, accessibility, convenience, portability, interactivity, and global presence are other major strengths of Hearst. According to Hearst (2020), "98% of its consumers care about environmental issues, 89% would be more likely to buy from a brand that values sustainability, and 87% have switched to reusable items".

Through innovative and thought-provoking content that actively encourages consumers to think about the environment and sustainable consumption, there is an opportunity for Hearst to engage and empower its audience. Additionally, virtual reality is another opportunity that is relatively new and has not been fully explored by competitors. Virtual reality is one area of the digital and fashion future that has a lot of potential. This new market will encompass both software and hardware. Like the role of social media in our lives now, virtual reality and augmented reality could undoubtedly become potent avenues for brand-consumer interactions. Goldman Sachs (2021) asserts that by 2025, the Virtual Reality/Augmented Reality business will generate \$182 billion in revenue.

Despite these opportunities, the cost-of-living crisis has had an effect on entertainment subscriptions, with 58% of individuals considering cancelling their digital subscriptions as a result of the economy. A digital subscription can be regarded as disposable as individuals become more frugal with their money, and this dynamic is evident in the digital magazines market (Mintel, 2022). In the three months leading up to September 2022, there was a 6-percentage-point dip in the proportion of digital readers who had purchased digital magazines (to 63%); this decline was mostly caused by a decline in the number of subscriptions to one title. Due to the problem with the cost of living, 32% of magazine readers have cancelled their subscriptions. (Mintel, 2022).

Regardless of these threats, as the saying goes, "doing good is good for business." High returns on investment can be achieved by becoming more sustainable and resilient. Major fashion companies are already leading the way in this transition. Burberry recently refinanced its revolving credit and linked it to important environmental, social, and governance (ESG) criteria. Mango likewise signed its first financial agreement, matching its ESG standards.

Gucci and its parent firm, Kering, have declared that they have been successful in decreasing their impact on the environment while growing sales. They do this by employing an Environmental Profit and Loss (EPL) account to track their impact (Intel, 2022). While these brands might not be digital media companies like Heart, their achievements show that there are benefits to brands taking an active stance on sustainability.

THEORY: THE THEORY OF PLANNED BEHAVIOUR

By highlighting the intermediary role of intention, Fishbein and Ajzen's work in the 1970s redefined the link between attitude and behaviour. The theories of reasoned action and planned behaviour (TRA and TPB) have radically altered the idea that attitudes directly transfer into behaviour. These theories have been implemented in a great deal of ethical context-specific research to help understand how consumers decide to act ethically. Researchers have frequently proposed and talked about the possibility of an intention-behavior gap in sustainable consumerism. (Hassan, Shiu and Shaw, 2016).

The theory of planned behaviour (TPB), which emerged from the theories of multiattribute attitude (TMA) and theory of reasoned action (TRA), is a social-psychological theory that describes the behavioural decision-making processes of individuals with the purpose of understanding and forecasting individual behaviour. It promotes the idea that human behaviour is primarily governed by the individual will (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1973). Hinging on the theory of reasoned action, which postulates that behavioural intention, along with attitude toward behaviour and subjective norm, are the two variables that influence intention, the TPB goes further to incorporate a metric of perceived behavioural control (PBC), which accounts for behaviours that are not under the volitional control of the individual. (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975), (Ajzen, 1985).

The past years have seen a significant development for TPB. The TPB theorist, Ajzen, published an analysis on the three main variables (attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioural control), as well as the three corresponding beliefs (behavioural belief, normative belief, and control belief), and they now make arguments to increase the model's rigour and scientificity. Ajzen and Fishbein (2004) noted the relative relevance of the three factors in predicting intention and that this prediction might alter owing to differences in behaviours and demographic groupings. They also note the distinct roles of the three variables in predicting intention and conduct. Only one or two of the three precursors may be essential for the prediction in some situations, rather than all three.

- **ATTITUDE:** Lim & Dubinshy (2005), buttressing Ajzen (1991) argues that the strongest indicator of behavioural intention is typically attitude. The individual nature, which is described as the positive or negative appraisal of individuals on the specific acts they engage in, i.e. the attitude of individuals, and the impact of society on individuals, are the two components in TPB that determine behavioural intention. The association between attitudes and behaviours is more pronounced the more detailed the attitudes and behaviours are (Ajzen&Fishbein, 1980).
- **SUBJECTIVE NORM:** includes the motivation to live up to others' social norms as well as attitudes about these ideals. In general, this refers to the perception of social pressure that leads one to act in line with social norms and decide whether to uphold others' opinions. Fishbein & Ajzen (1975) assert that the subjective norm is the least powerful factor that drives behaviour, but its influence on undesirable conduct, such as wasting food and water, patronising unethical businesses, and so on, is highly substantial.
- **PERCEIVED BEHAVIOURAL CONTROL:** The 1977 self-efficacy theory of Bandura is commonly regarded as the source of perceived behavioural control. When people engage in certain behaviours, they perceive themselves to have some degree of control over their actions. This perception is influenced by three variables: capabilities, resources, and opportunities (Ajzen, 1985). The stronger the perception of an individual's ability to manage their behaviour, the more capabilities, resources, and opportunities they believe they possess to carry out certain actions. In contrast, people will not have a strong intention to carry out the act if they lack the ability, finances, or chances to do so, or if comparable prior experiences have led them to believe that doing so will be challenging. The persistent use of perceived behavioural control as a substitute for actual control assessment demonstrates a clear link between PBC and behavioural achievement.
- **BELIEF:** Control beliefs, normative views, and behavioural beliefs were classified by Ajzen (1991); Doll & Ajzen (1992). In line with Armitage and Conner's (2001) meta-analysis, behavioural beliefs, normative beliefs, and control beliefs can each account for 25% of the variation in attitude, 25% of the variation in the subjective norm, and 27% of the variation in perceived behaviour control. All other internal elements (such as personality, IQ, experience, age, gender, etc.) and external ones (such as knowledge, context, cultural background, etc.) have a direct impact on beliefs, which in turn influence attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN INTENTION AND BEHAVIOR

Further exploring the ambiguity of the relationship between intention and behaviour, Ajzen et al. (2009) found that people don't always behave in line with their initial intentions. Through empirical study, they found that there was a difficult gap between behaviour and intention and that there were at least three key ideas to consider when putting them into practice: intention, commitment, and conscientiousness (Ajzen et al., 2009). A sort of connection was established for the planned behaviour by the implementation intention, according to the link between the three concepts (belief, norms, and PBC), intents, and actions, which significantly boosted people's conscientiousness and level of task performance. Individuals with high conscientiousness are more likely than those with low conscientiousness to display this trait (Ajzen et al, 2009).

The meta-analysis by Bogg and Robert (2004) provided support for the claim by showing that, in contrast to people with low conscientiousness, people with high conscientiousness rarely participate in a dangerous activity and are more likely to engage in healthy behaviour. This claim that conscientiousness might change the link between intention and behaviour was also validated by Rhodes et al. (2005). In order to close the gap between intention and behaviour, Ajzen (2009) suggested that two different types of interventions might be needed, with one intervention's goal being to produce a particular type of desired intention and the other being to encourage the performance associated with the desired behaviour.

LIMITATIONS

TPB has shown various limits and flaws in long-term practice, like any theoretical model. The unexplainable behavioural variances should not be exclusively attributed to random mistakes; there should still be some unmeasured elements, so it appears that not all social behaviours can be described by TPB. East (2000) noted that TPB in the retail setting did not appear to indicate the propensity for product complaints.

A major drawback of TPB, as noted by Bergman (2005), is that in contrast to other theories of emotional processing, TPB seems to dismiss emotions like threats, fear, and positive or negative sensations with very few grounds supporting them. To further confirm this notion, Armitage et al. (1999) specifically tested whether mood may significantly influence attitude, subjective norm, perceived behaviour control, and intention. Armitage et al.'s (1999) findings revealed that while the subjective norm is more likely to be closely associated with intention when the individual is in a positive emotional state, the attitude is more likely to be closely related to intention when the participant is in a negative emotional state. Zhang (2018) further argues that the ability to forecast behaviour should take into account both positive and negative emotions. Furthermore, stress appears to be able to restrict and decrease connections between intention and action. For instance, when individuals are under a lot of stress at work, their desire to exercise barely influences what they actually do (Payne, Jones & Harris, 2002).

In addition, Zhang (2018) indicates that further study should focus on how the TPB can be used to describe the link between behaviour and emotion, arguing that the TPB can only be applied to describe individual logical behaviour. However, no human behaviour can be based on emotion from a physiological perspective. The autonomic nervous system-based emotional response occurs first and lays the stage for the ensuing cognitive response. Hence, the ideal TPB model based on logical individual behaviour cannot adequately account for the emotional conduct of a person. (Zhang, 2018).

Aside from taking emotions into account, Zhang (2018) criticises TPB for failing to consider the impact of differences between individuals and cultures. The fundamental premise of TPB is that people are considered to be homogenous individuals who actualise behavioural intention decisions based on three modules: attitude, subjective norm, and PBC. Elements of individual, cultural, and contextual heterogeneity are thus omitted from the theoretical model. TPB diminishes or even ignores the unique characteristics of human behaviour when forecasting using a linear model.

MODIFICATION

A modified application of the theory is anticipated to be more appropriate for Hearst after taking into account the critique that has been given. A major criticism of this theory is its focus on individual rational behaviour (Zhang, 2018). To this end, this report proposes a fusion of the theory of planned behaviour and consumer imagination and desire theory.

The potential of the imagination to explain both individual market behaviours and changes in market structure is frequently disregarded in marketing, despite it being a distinctive and important part of human nature. (Jenkins and Molesworth, 2018). Imagination, in Sutton-Smith's (1997) words, is "the act of making what is present absent or what is absent present." According to Scott (1994), consumer researchers have ignored an important aspect of the human mental experience—the work of the imagination. Martin (2004) affirms Scott's point, asserting that by focusing on consumption, information processing ignores the imagination. The aforementioned shows several researchers' observations, suggesting that the imagination is underrepresented in consumer research.

Jenkins and Molesworth (2018), highlighting previous studies, explain that consumers experience pleasure through imagining. The focus on how consumerism influences the imagination has become more critical. Considering Soper's (2007) work on alternative hedonism and Schor's (1998) work on voluntary simplicity, customers may have diverse conceptions of the "happy life." It is necessary to shift from looking at needs to desires, from information processing to imagination (mindset) and daydreaming (Belk et al. 2003, Campbell 1987, Jenkins and Molesworth 2018). While it is acknowledged that daydreaming is intentional, activated on

demand, and uncontrolled, allowing consumers to "choose" to daydream (Campbell, 1987), stimuli may cause distraction away from the most crucial elements of reality and toward spontaneous daydreams, making their occurrence not random.

The media is a typical example of these stimuli; as consumers rely on the media to feed their imaginations and desires, the media in turn invites consumers to imagine just how much better their lives could be. Advertising provides resources for the imagination (Belk et al. 2003; Jenkins and Molesworth 2018). As regards contents, Hearst can use Soper's (2008) take on alternative hedonism and Csikszentmihaly's (2000) flow theory to trigger and stimulate consumers' imaginations about sustainable consumption, as these theories prioritize the planet and people.

Content of imagination	Characteristics of imagination	
	Spontaneous	Controlled
<i>Uninstructed</i> (imaging)	Daydreams	Narrative transportation (experience-taking)
<i>Marketer-instructed</i> (imagine-that)	Consumption daydreams	Mental simulation (self-referencing)
<i>Marketer-instructed process-focused</i> (imagine-how)	Visualization	Process-focused simulation (mental-practicing)

RECOMMENDATION

A reasonable approach to tackling the issue identified is to simplify the choice of words used when discussing sustainable consumption. It is important to note that, however simplified, the choice of words must provide well-detailed and accurate information without boring or overloading consumers.

Basically, it is recommended that Hearst find a balance between concrete and abstract appeal and incorporate this balance into its contents in order to close the intention-behaviour gap.

CONCLUSION

Does this report overcomplicate customer behaviour? Is this approach overly strategic? The reason for adopting this notion is supported by a wealth of well-defined research on both theories. Hence, proving the validity and reliability of this school of thought. Adopting this hybrid approach will not only help Hearst create strong lifestyle associations for sustainable consumption in the fashion industry but also help consumers make better dreams by creating aesthetically pleasing images and using compelling narrative devices—language.

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